

ALIGNING LANGUAGE ASSESSMENT WITH THE CEFR. A PRACTICAL FRAMEWORK

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Abstract: The CEFR has had a more profound impact than originally anticipated on teachers, learners and researchers from a diversity of linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Due to the sophisticated theoretical framework underlying it, the interpretation and implementation of the CEFR may be challenging to language teaching practitioners outside Europe, especially those who are English as a foreign language (EFL) learners themselves and are used to more traditional teacher-centered language teaching and learning. The main purpose of this paper is to discuss the use of the CEFR in the field of language assessment, with a particular focus on issues related to the alignment of assessments with the CEFR. Before discussing alignment issues, however, it is important to first consider the work that led to the development of the CEFR and its levels, which is presented in the next section

Keywords: *CEFR, Language assessment, Alignment with CEFR, Teacher-centered learning, Council of Europe*

Annotatsiya: CEFR turli til va madaniy kelib chiqishi bo'lgan o'qituvchilar, o'quvchilar va tadqiqotchilarga dastlab kutilganidan ko'ra chuqurroq ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Uning asosida yotgan murakkab nazariy asos tufayli, CEFRni talqin qilish va amalga oshirish Yevropadan tashqarida til o'rgatuvchi amaliyotchilar, ayniqsa ingliz tilini chet tili (EFL) sifatida o'rganuvchilar uchun qiyin bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsadi tilni baholash sohasida CEFRdan foydalanishni muhokama qilishdan iborat bo'lib, baholashlarni CEFR bilan moslashtirish bilan bog'liq masalalarga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi. Biroq, muvofiqlashtirish masalalarini muhokama qilishdan oldin, birinchi navbatda, keyingi bo'limda keltirilgan CEFR va uning darajalarini ishlab chiqishga olib kelgan ishlarni ko'rib chiqish muhimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: CEFR, tilni baholash, CEFR bilan moslashish, o'qituvchiga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim, Yevropa kengashi

Аннотация: Всеобщая рамочная программа оценки языковых компетенций (CEFR) оказала более глубокое влияние, чем предполагалось изначально, на преподавателей, учащихся и исследователей из самых разных языковых и культурных слоев. Из-за сложной теоретической основы, лежащей в ее основе, интерпретация и применение CEFR могут представлять собой сложную задачу для преподавателей языков за пределами Европы, особенно для тех, кто сам изучает английский как иностранный язык (EFL) и привык к более традиционному, ориентированному на преподавателя, подходу к обучению языку. Основная

цель данной статьи — обсудить использование CEFR в области оценки языковых навыков, уделяя особое внимание вопросам, связанным с согласованием оценок с CEFR. Однако, прежде чем обсуждать вопросы согласования, важно сначала рассмотреть работу, которая привела к разработке CEFR и ее уровней, которая представлена в следующем разделе.

Ключевые слова: CEFR, оценка языковых навыков, согласование с CEFR, обучение, ориентированное на преподавателя, Совет Европы

CEFR Informed Learning, Teaching and Assessment: A Practical Guide, as the title suggests, systematically guides the reader through the three topics. In order to promote plurilingualism and pluriculturalism among European citizens, the Council of Europe published a number of documents in the 1970s that have been influential in second language teaching, such as the notional-functional syllabus by Wilkins, which describes what a learner communicates through language (Wilkins 1976), and three ascending levels describing language achievement: Waystage (Van Ek and Trim 1991), Threshold (Van Ek and Trim 1998) and Vantage (Van Ek and Trim 2001). In 1991, at an intergovernmental symposium in Switzerland, the development of a common framework for learning, teaching and assessment was deemed desirable in order to:

- promote and facilitate cooperation among educational institutions in different countries;
- provide a sound basis for the mutual recognition of language qualifications;
- assist learners, teachers, course designers, examining bodies and educational administrators in situating and coordinating their efforts; (Council of Europe 2001: 5)

Although the CEFR contains a rich description of the language learning process, it is widely accepted that the CEFR language proficiency scales are the best known part of the 2001 volume (Little 2006). The proficiency scales of the CEFR have gained popularity because they offer a comprehensive description of the objectives that learners can expect to achieve at different levels of language proficiency. They describe language activities and competences at six main levels: A1 (the lowest) through A2, B1, B2, C1 to C2 (the highest). Borderline levels are further elaborated using a 'plus' between A2+ (between A2 and B1), B1+ (between B1 and B2) and B2+ (between B2 and C1). The scales comprise statements called 'descriptors', which are always phrased positively, as they are intended to motivate learners by describing what they can do when they use the language, rather than what they cannot do (Council of Europe 2001: 205). The performance descriptors of the CEFR are designed following an action-oriented approach: language users are seen as members of a society who have tasks to accomplish, including those that are not language-related (Council of Europe 2001: 9).

Nowadays, providers of language assessments, both inside and outside Europe, follow various methodologies to align their assessments with the CEFR levels, as reported in several case studies in two edited volumes (Figueras and Noijons 2009; Martyniuk 2010). The most common approach to bring tests into

alignment with the CEFR is the one recommended in the Manual published by the Council of Europe (2009). The approach consists of two main stages: content alignment and setting of cut scores.

CEFR-informed learner autonomy. The central focus in this chapter is the European Language Portfolio (ELP), which is introduced to serve the purposes of facilitating learners' understanding of the abstract concepts in the CEFR, and developing their plurilingual awareness, pluricultural awareness and capacity for autonomous language learning. This chapter focuses on the functions, types, and applications of the components of the ELP. The exercises that follow further familiarize the reader with the components of the ELP and the steps involved in designing them. Three case studies are also presented to demonstrate how to implement and contextualize ELPs for particular pedagogic purposes. This chapter shows in considerable detail how the ELP mediates the core concepts of the CEFR to the learner, and how teachers may support and guide learners in fulfilling the aims of the CEFR. Based on a separate analysis of CEFR-informed teaching, assessment and learning integration of the three processes in light of the CEFR. The action-oriented approach adopted by the CEFR integrates the three processes with a common definition of language proficiency by means of real-world "tasks represented by CEFR 'can-do' descriptors". This culminates in the discussion of the implementation of integrated CEFR-informed learning, assessment and teaching, for which learning outcome statements and a checklist of illustrative descriptors need to be developed to inform lesson plans and autonomous learning, as well as learner self-assessment and teacher assessment. The exercises illustrate the importance of ensuring the validity of CEFR implementation in classroom teaching and assessment. The case studies exemplify the integration of task-based language teaching, the CEFR and learning-oriented assessment in a learning cycle, and a contextualized development of intercultural and communicative language competences, respectively. The discussion provides a multifaceted picture of the goal-oriented implementation of the CEFR in language teaching, assessment and learning, highlighting the transparency and coherence as it claims.

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